

Unveiling the Potential: Exploring Machine Learning Classifiers for Lung Cancer Prediction

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Abstract— This study investigates the application of machine learning algorithms for lung cancer detection using a dataset obtained from Kaggle, comprising demographic and clinical features. Preprocessing steps include handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, and selecting pertinent features associated with lung cancer risk factors. Various classifiers, including logistic regression, decision trees, SVM etc. are evaluated based on performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Results indicate that SVM and LDA demonstrate superior performance showing potential for further improvement. These findings underscore the significance of machine learning in enhancing lung cancer detection and highlight avenues for future research in refining classifier selection and ensemble techniques for improved diagnostic accuracy also this study presents promising prospects for integrating machine learning algorithms into clinical practice for improved lung cancer management

Keywords— Lung cancer detection, Machine learning, Classifier comparison, Performance metrics, Diagnostic accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, emphasizing the critical need for early detection and effective treatment strategies. Machine learning techniques offer promising avenues for enhancing lung cancer detection [11] accuracy through the analysis of various patient attributes and risk factors. In this study, we investigate the efficacy of different machine learning classifiers in accurately predicting lung cancer based on a comprehensive set of patient attributes, including demographic information, smoking history, and symptoms. Additionally, we explore the impact of feature selection and on improving classifier performance and reducing the risk of overfitting. By evaluating the performance of diverse classifiers, we aim to provide valuable insights into optimal approaches for lung cancer detection and diagnosis [12].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] explored the use of machine learning algorithms to predict lung cancer. They compared several algorithms and identified the most effective one for their dataset. Their findings suggest that machine learning holds promise for lung cancer prediction, potentially aiding early diagnosis and improved patient outcomes. [2] underscores the critical need for early detection of lung cancer to mitigate global mortality rates. It introduces an algorithm designed to accurately segment lung tumors in CT images using image processing techniques and a Support Vector Machine classifier for classification. [3] proposes a methodology that exhibits enhanced performance in identifying lymph node involvement on histopathological slides, with superior accuracy compared to existing algorithms. [4] provides an overview of machine learning-based approaches aimed at improving various facets of lung cancer diagnosis and therapy, while also discussing future challenges and opportunities for utilizing machine learning in this field. [5] explores methods for lung cancer detection, emphasizing early identification's critical role in treatment. Utilizing image processing and machine learning techniques, particularly the ANN model, it achieves accurate classification and prediction of lung cancer, showcasing advancements in medical technology. [6] describes the development of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) designed to detect the presence or absence of lung cancer based on symptoms and other input variables. Utilizing a dataset titled "survey lung cancer," the trained ANN achieved an accuracy of 96.67% in diagnosing lung cancer. [7] addresses the significance of early detection in lung cancer survival rates and evaluates various classification algorithms such as Naive Bayes, SVM, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression for predicting lung cancer. It

underscores the importance of early diagnosis in mitigating the mortality rate of lung cancer by analyzing the performance of these algorithms.[8] synthesizes recent research on deep learning applications in lung cancer detection from CT scans, showcasing the superior performance of deep learning models over traditional methods. Despite promising results, challenges such as model dependence on training data and interpretability issues underscore the need for continued research to ensure the reliability and applicability of these models in clinical settings. [9] presents a hybrid framework for lung cancer diagnosis from CT images, incorporating Discrete Local Binary Pattern (DLBP) and Hybrid Wavelet Partial Hadamard Transform (Hybrid WPHT) techniques, along with optimization methods like adaptive Harris-Hawk optimization (AHHO) and improved weight-based beetle swarm (IW-BS) algorithm, achieving superior accuracy and efficiency in categorizing lung CT images as normal, benign, or malignant. [10] utilizes machine learning methods, particularly Rotation Forest, to develop efficient models for identifying individuals at high risk of developing lung cancer, enabling earlier interventions to mitigate long-term complications. Evaluation experiments demonstrate the proposed model's superior performance with high metrics including an AUC of 99.3%, F-Measure, precision, recall, and accuracy of 97.1%.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our study focuses on developing an accurate predictive model for lung cancer detection utilizing machine learning methodologies [13]. Initially, we obtained a comprehensive dataset from Kaggle, comprising various patient attributes such as gender, age, smoking history, and an array of symptoms associated with lung cancer, including fatigue, wheezing, and chest pain. The dataset underwent meticulous preprocessing, including handling missing values and encoding categorical variables, ensuring its suitability for analysis. Given the inherent class imbalance in medical datasets, we addressed this challenge by employing the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE)[14]. By oversampling the minority class (lung cancer-positive cases) and synthesizing new instances using interpolation techniques, SMOTE effectively balanced the dataset, mitigating biases towards the majority class.

Our approach prioritized a diverse set of machine learning algorithms, including Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forests, Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). Each classifier underwent training on the dataset and subsequent evaluation utilizing a range of metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, assessed on both validation and test datasets. This thorough evaluation facilitated the identification of the most effective classifiers for lung cancer prediction. In this analysis, the feature selection strategy employed is based on the Lasso (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) algorithm. Through a systematic comparison of different classifiers, our study aims to provide valuable insights into optimal strategies for accurate lung cancer prediction. Such insights could potentially assist healthcare professionals in early detection and diagnosis of lung cancer, ultimately improving patient outcomes. Fig.1 shows the methodology of work done.

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of Methodology

A. Preprocessing

The preprocessing steps in this study began with the removal of duplicate entries to ensure data integrity and prevent bias in subsequent analyses. Although no missing values were present in the dataset [22], addressing duplicates was paramount to eliminate redundant information and maintain the k's consistency. Categorical variables were then encoded into numerical format using techniques like one-hot encoding, facilitating their integration into machine learning models.

B. Class Imbalance Handling

UMAP [15] can reveal the degree of separation between classes in a lower-dimensional space. Balanced datasets often exhibit distinct clusters for each class, while imbalanced datasets may show overlapping or unevenly distributed clusters. Through UMAP visualization, these differences become apparent, providing insights into the level of class separation. Fig. 2 shows the visualization of target variable in the dataset. In dealing with class imbalance, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) was employed as a pivotal preprocessing step. SMOTE works by generating synthetic samples from the minority class, thereby balancing the class distribution and mitigating the effects of class imbalance. By oversampling the minority class, SMOTE effectively increases the representation of minority instances in the dataset, ensuring that the machine learning algorithms are trained on a more balanced and representative dataset. This approach helps prevent the model from being biased towards the majority class and improves its ability to accurately classify instances from both classes. By addressing class imbalance through SMOTE, the study aimed to enhance the performance and generalization ability of the machine learning models, ultimately leading to more robust and reliable predictions.

Fig .2: Dataset Visualisation using UMAP

C. Feature Selection and Classification

In this analysis, the feature selection strategy leverages the Lasso (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) algorithm [16]. Mathematically, Lasso is formulated as in the equation 1:

$$\text{minimize } (1/2n \|y - X\beta\|_2^2 + \alpha\|\beta\|_1) \quad (1)$$

Here, y represents the target variable, X is the feature matrix, β is the coefficient vector to be estimated, $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the L2-norm, and $\|\cdot\|_1$ represents the L1-norm. The parameter α controls the amount of regularization applied. Lasso's objective function consists of two terms: the first term corresponds to the residual sum of squares, measuring the discrepancy between the observed and predicted values, while the second term is the L1 penalty, encouraging sparsity in the coefficient vector β . By minimizing this objective function, Lasso simultaneously performs feature selection (by shrinking some coefficients to zero) and regularization (to prevent overfitting).

In this work, a comprehensive evaluation of various classification algorithms was conducted to identify the most effective model for predicting lung cancer based on a set of features including demographic information and medical history. The study employed a diverse range of classifiers such as Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors, Naive Bayes, Neural Network, AdaBoost, XGBoost, Gaussian Process, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA). These classifiers represent a broad spectrum of machine learning techniques, including both linear and nonlinear models, and probabilistic classifiers. Each algorithm was trained and evaluated using standard metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score to assess its performance in classifying lung cancer cases. By comparing the results across different classifiers, the study aimed to identify the most accurate and reliable model for lung cancer prediction, providing valuable insights for clinical diagnosis and treatment planning.

D. Performance Evaluation

The performance evaluation of the classifiers was conducted using various metrics to assess their effectiveness in predicting lung cancer. The evaluation metrics included accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which provide a comprehensive assessment of the classifier's performance across different aspects of classification accuracy and error. Accuracy measures the overall correctness of the classifier's predictions, while precision quantifies the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions made by the classifier. Recall, also known as sensitivity, measures the proportion of true positive predictions among all actual positive instances in the dataset. F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced measure of the classifier's performance in terms of both false positives and false negatives. By evaluating classifiers based on these metrics, the study aimed to identify the models that achieve the highest levels of accuracy and reliability in predicting lung cancer, thereby guiding clinical decision-making and improving patient outcomes.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) achieves the highest total score, indicating superior performance among the evaluated models. Following LDA, Support Vector Machine (SVM) emerges as the second-highest ranked classifier. This ranking suggests that LDA exhibits the most favorable combination of evaluation metrics, including validation accuracy, test accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, among others. SVM also demonstrates strong performance across these metrics but falls slightly behind LDA in

overall ranking [17]. This information provides valuable insights for selecting the most effective classifier for lung cancer prediction tasks, with LDA and SVM standing out as top-performing options. Fig. 3 shows the comparison of various classifiers.

Fig. 3: Comparison of various classifiers

The ranking of classifiers involves a meticulous process of assigning weights to different evaluation metrics, each reflecting a specific aspect of classifier performance. Metrics such as validation accuracy, test accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are considered, with weights allocated based on their relative importance in assessing classifier effectiveness. Metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which directly measure the classifier's ability to correctly classify instances, are assigned higher weights, emphasizing their significance in evaluating performance. Conversely, metrics related to execution time and model size receive lower weights, as their impact on classifier performance is less critical. Negative weights may be assigned to these metrics to indicate a preference for lower values, ensuring a balanced consideration of trade-offs between performance and computational efficiency.

Once weights are defined, the weighted scores for each classifier are computed by multiplying the corresponding metric values by their respective weights. These weighted scores are then aggregated to calculate the total score for each classifier, providing a holistic assessment of its performance across multiple dimensions. Finally, classifiers are ranked based on their total score in ascending order, with lower scores indicating superior performance as shown in Fig. 4. This comprehensive ranking approach offers valuable insights into the relative strengths and weaknesses of different classifiers, aiding in the selection of the most suitable model for lung cancer prediction tasks and facilitating informed decision-making in model selection. Additionally, the accompanying figure visually represents the ranking of various classifiers, offering a clear and intuitive representation of their comparative performance.

Fig. 4: Ranking of Classifiers

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, as outlined in [18], offers a comprehensive depiction of a binary classification model's performance, illustrating the balance between its True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR) across varying threshold settings as shown in Fig. 5. Each point on the curve corresponds to a specific threshold, demonstrating how adjustments in the threshold influence the model's ability to accurately classify positive and negative instances. A perfect classifier would attain a TPR of 1.0 and an FPR of 0.0, positioning a point at the top-left corner of the ROC space, while a classifier performing no better than chance would yield a diagonal line, indicating an equal chance of true and false positives.

The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) condenses the ROC curve's performance into a single metric, offering a holistic assessment of the model's discriminatory ability. AUC values range from 0.5 (denoting random guessing) to 1.0 (denoting perfect classification), with higher scores indicative of superior model performance. Curves situated further from the diagonal line towards the top-left corner signify enhanced discrimination between positive and negative instances. Interpreting the ROC curve and AUC aids in evaluating the classification model's effectiveness, facilitating the selection of appropriate threshold values to strike the desired balance between TPR and FPR for specific applications or problem domains.

Fig. 5: RoC of various classifiers with lasso = 0.035

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CLASSIFIERS

Classifier	Lasso=0.035				Lasso=0.038			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Logistic Regression	85.48	93.55	80.56	86.57	85.48	93.54	80.55	86.57
Decision Tree	79.03	87.10	75.00	80.60	82.25	90.32	77.77	83.58
Random Forest	82.66	93.33	77.78	84.85	82.25	90.32	77.77	83.58
Gradient Boosting	82.26	93.10	75.00	83.08	82.25	93.10	75.00	83.07
SVM	83.87	90.63	80.56	85.29	83.87	90.62	80.55	85.29
K-Nearest Neighbors	83.87	90.63	80.56	85.29	83.87	90.62	80.55	85.29
Naive Bayes	85.48	90.91	83.33	86.96	85.48	90.90	83.33	86.96
Neural Network	85.48	90.91	80.56	86.96	85.48	93.55	80.55	86.57
AdaBoost	83.87	93.33	77.78	84.85	83.87	93.33	77.77	84.84

XGBoost	84.85	82.26	96.30	72.22	82.26	96.3	72.22	82.54
Gaussian Process	85.48	93.55	80.56	86.57	85.48	93.55	80.55	86.57
LDA	85.48	93.55	80.56	86.57	85.48	93.55	80.55	86.57
QDA	83.57	90.63	80.56	85.29	83.87	90.62	80.55	85.29

Electing the "best" value of Lasso regularization parameter (alpha) depends on the specific goals and priorities of the task. The justification for considering an alpha value of 0.038 as potentially striking a balance between simplicity and performance lies in the observed outcomes when compared to other alpha values and their respective effects on feature selection and model evaluation metrics. If the objective is to balance model simplicity with predictive performance, a moderate value of alpha such as 0.035 or 0.038 might be suitable. These values resulted in a moderate number of selected features (8 or 5), which could strike a balance between simplicity and performance. The evaluation metrics for various machine learning models, such as Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, etc., remain relatively stable across different values of alpha as shown in Table I. This consistency suggests that the model's predictive performance is not significantly compromised with a moderate reduction in the number of features. In other words, the models maintain a good balance between simplicity (achieved through feature reduction) and performance (as indicated by stable evaluation metrics). The top 10 features selected by lasso is shown in Figure Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Selected features by feature importance

When applying Lasso regularization with a parameter value of 0.035, a total of 10 features are selected from the dataset as shown in Fig. 6. These features are deemed the most relevant for predicting the target variable while simultaneously mitigating the risk of overfitting by penalizing the coefficients of less significant features. Among the selected features, the presence of "Chronic Disease" stands out as it consistently appears in all cases, irrespective of variations in the Lasso regularization parameter [19][20]. This suggests that "Chronic Disease" holds a high level of significance in predicting the target variable across different regularization strengths. The consistent inclusion of "Chronic Disease" across various Lasso regularization

values underscores its strong predictive power and influence on the target variable. It implies that "Chronic Disease" plays a pivotal role in distinguishing between different classes or outcomes of the target variable. Furthermore, as the Lasso regularization parameter increases, the number of selected features tends to decrease. This reduction in the number of features indicates a stronger regularization effect, emphasizing a preference for a simpler model with fewer predictors while maintaining predictive performance. Overall, the persistent inclusion of "Chronic Disease" highlights its critical importance in the predictive model, emphasizing its relevance and impact on the target variable across different regularization settings.

Fig. 7: Performance of classifiers on selected features

The analysis employing Lasso regularization for feature selection in predicting lung cancer revealed chronic disease indicators as pivotal factors across various classifiers. These features consistently demonstrated high importance scores and contributed significantly to accurate predictions, underscoring their relevance in the classification task. The findings suggest that considering the presence of chronic diseases alongside other clinical variables can enhance the precision of lung cancer diagnosis and prognosis as shown in Fig. 7. This highlights the potential of leveraging comorbidity information to refine risk assessment strategies and tailor treatment approaches, ultimately improving patient outcomes and healthcare decision-making in the context of lung cancer management.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In conclusion, this study presents a comprehensive analysis of various machine learning classifiers for the prediction of lung cancer based on a dataset obtained from Kaggle. Through rigorous experimentation and

performance evaluation, it was found that Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) emerged as the top-performing classifiers, exhibiting high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of considering multiple evaluation metrics and classifier rankings to identify the most suitable model for lung cancer prediction tasks. Moreover, the implementation of preprocessing techniques, such as handling class imbalance and removing duplicates, significantly contributes to enhancing the overall performance of the classifiers.

Looking ahead, future research could explore advanced feature selection methods to further optimize model performance and reduce computational complexity. Additionally, incorporating deep learning techniques and leveraging larger datasets could potentially improve the accuracy and robustness of lung cancer prediction models. Furthermore, extending this work to incorporate real-time data streams and integrating with clinical decision support systems could have significant implications for early diagnosis and personalized treatment strategies for lung cancer patients. Overall, this study lays the groundwork for continued exploration and innovation in the field of lung cancer prediction using machine learning approaches.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. S. Raouf, M. A. Jabbar and S. A. Fathima, "Lung Cancer Prediction using Machine Learning: A Comprehensive Approach," *2020 2nd International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry Applications (ICIMIA)*, Bangalore, India, 2020, pp. 108-115, doi: 10.1109/ICIMIA48430.2020.9074947..
- [2] S. Janee Alam and A. Hossan, "Multi-Stage Lung Cancer Detection and Prediction Using Multi-class SVM Classifier", *2018 International Conference on Computer Communication Chemical Material and Electronic Engineering (IC4ME2)*.
- [3] Vani Rajasekar, M.P. Vaishnave, S. Premkumar, Velliangiri Sarveshwaran, V. Rangaraaj, Lung cancer disease prediction with CT scan and histopathological images feature analysis using deep learning techniques, *Results in Engineering*, Volume 18, 2023, ISSN 2590-1230, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2023.101111>
- [4] Li Y, Wu X, Yang P, Jiang G, Luo Y. Machine Learning for Lung Cancer Diagnosis, Treatment, and Prognosis. *Genomics Proteomics Bioinformatics*. 2022 Oct;20(5):850-866. doi: 10.1016/j.gpb.2022.11.003. Epub 2022 Dec 1. PMID: 36462630; PMCID: PMC10025752.
- [5] Nageswaran S, Arunkumar G, Bisht AK, Mewada S, Kumar JNVRS, Jawarneh M, Asenso E. Lung Cancer Classification and Prediction Using Machine Learning and Image Processing. *Biomed Res Int*. 2022 Aug 22;2022:1755460. doi: 10.1155/2022/1755460.
- [6] Nasser, Ibrahim M. and Abu-Naser, Samy S., Lung Cancer Detection Using Artificial Neural Network (March 2019). *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS)*, 3(3), 17-23, March 2019, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3369062>
- [7] R. P.R., R. A. S. Nair and V. G., "A Comparative Study of Lung Cancer Detection using Machine Learning Algorithms," *2019 IEEE International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT)*, Coimbatore, India, 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICECCT.2019.8869001.
- [8] Gayap, Hadrien T., and Moulay A. Akhloufi. 2024. "Deep Machine Learning for Medical Diagnosis, Application to Lung Cancer Detection: A Review" *BioMedInformatics* 4, no. 1: 236-284. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedinformatics4010015>.
- [9] N Venkatesan, S Pasupathy, B Gobinathan, An efficient lung cancer detection using optimal SVM and improved weight based beetle swarm optimization, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, Volume 88, 2024, ISSN 1746-8094, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2023.105373>.
- [10] A. Karnik, "Performance of TCP congestion control with rate feedback: TCP/ABR and rate adaptive TCP/IP," M. Eng. thesis, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India, Jan. 1999.
- [10] Dritsas, Elias, and Maria Trigka. 2022. "Lung Cancer Risk Prediction with Machine Learning Models" *Big Data and Cognitive Computing* 6, no. 4: 139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc6040139>.
- [11] B. S, P. R and A. B, "Lung Cancer Detection using Machine Learning," *2022 International Conference on Applied Artificial Intelligence and Computing (ICAAIC)*, Salem, India, 2022, pp. 539-543, doi: 10.1109/ICAAIC53929.2022.9793061.
- [12] Nooreldeen, Reem, and Horacio Bach. 2021. "Current and Future Development in Lung Cancer Diagnosis" *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22, no. 16: 8661. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms2216866>
- [13] Patra, R. (2020). Prediction of Lung Cancer Using Machine Learning Classifier. In: Chaubey, N., Parikh, S., Amin, K. (eds) *Computing Science, Communication and Security. COMS2 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol 1235. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-6648-6_11
- [14] Blagus, R., Lusa, L. SMOTE for high-dimensional class-imbalanced data. *BMC Bioinformatics* 14, 106 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-14-106>
- [15] Leland McInnes and John Healy and James Melville, UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction, arXiv, 2020.
- [16] Hui Zou (2006) The Adaptive Lasso and Its Oracle Properties, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 101:476, 1418-1429, DOI: [10.1198/016214506000000735](https://doi.org/10.1198/016214506000000735)
- [17] Bhatt, Nikita, Amit Thakkar, Amit Ganatra, and Nirav Bhatt. "Ranking of classifiers based on dataset characteristics using active meta learning." *International Journal of Computer Applications* 69, no. 20 (2013).
- [18] Metz, Charles E. "Basic principles of ROC analysis." In *Seminars in nuclear medicine*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 283-298. WB Saunders, 1978.
- [19] Takiguchi, Yuichi, Ikuo Sekine, Shunichiro Iwasawa, Ryota Kurimoto, and Koichiro Tatsumi. "Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease as a risk factor for lung cancer." *World journal of clinical oncology* 5, no. 4 (2014): 660.
- [20] Adcock, Ian M., Gaetano Caramori, and Peter J. Barnes. "Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and lung cancer: new molecular insights." *Respiration* 81, no. 4 (2011): 265-284.
- [21] Kaggle Survey lung cancer dataset <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/jillanisofttech/lung-cancer-detection?resource=download>